

ASSESSING THE NEED FOR VALUES COUNSELLING AMONG HIGHER EDUCATION STUDENTS IN INDIA: A SURVEY STUDY

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Abstract

This survey study aims to assess the need for values counselling among higher education students in India. The study aims to examine the impact of counselling interventions on students' values, attitudes, and behaviors. By understanding the potential benefits of values counselling, educators and policymakers can design effective intervention programs to promote holistic development among Indian higher education students.

Keywords: Values, counselling, higher education, India.

Introduction

Values play a crucial role in shaping an individual's identity, behavior and decision-making process. In the context of higher education, where students are exposed to diverse experiences and ideologies, counselling interventions focused on values can help students navigate their personal and academic lives effectively. India, being a culturally diverse nation, requires a comprehensive understanding of the specific values-related challenges faced by higher education students and the potential benefits of counselling in addressing these challenges. This study aims to bridge this gap by investigating the need for values counselling among Indian higher education students.

Objectives of the study

- Assess the existing values framework among higher education students in India.
- Determine the specific values-related challenges faced by higher education students in India.
- Evaluate the impact of values counselling interventions on students' values, attitudes, and behaviors.
- Identify the key components of an effective values counselling program for Indian higher education students.

Review of Literature

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Research Methodology

In the data collection phase of a survey study, we have employed various methods, depending on the nature of the survey question and the objectives of the study. Here are some methods of data collection:

1. Surveys/Questionnaires: Surveys involve the administration of a set of standardized questions to a sample of participants. The survey instrument should be carefully designed, taking into account the objectives and ensuring clarity and relevance of the questions. The reliability and validity of the survey can be established through pilot testing, test-retest reliability, and content validity assessments.

2. Interviews: Interviews can be conducted in-person, over the phone, or through online platforms. They can be structured (using predetermined questions), semi-structured (allowing flexibility while covering key topics), or unstructured (open-ended and exploratory). Interview protocols should be developed to guide the conversation, and reliability can be enhanced through interviewer training and inter-rater reliability checks.
3. Observations: Observational methods involve systematically observing and recording behaviors, interactions, or events in natural or controlled settings. Protocols should be developed to standardize the observation process, including the behaviors to be observed, the context, and the recording methods. Inter-rater reliability can be established through independent observations by multiple observers and subsequent comparison of results.

The study will include a diverse sample of higher education students from different universities and colleges across India. Participants will be recruited through a purposive sampling technique to ensure representation from different geographical regions, socio-economic backgrounds, and disciplines.

Table 1: Sample Size and Demographics

Demographic Variable	Sample Size
Geographical Region	
<i>North India</i>	200
<i>South India</i>	200
<i>East India</i>	200
<i>West India</i>	200
Socio-economic Background	
<i>Low-income</i>	200
<i>Middle-income</i>	200
<i>High-income</i>	200
Disciplines	
<i>Science</i>	200
<i>Arts</i>	200
<i>Commerce</i>	200
<i>Engineering</i>	200
<i>Medicine</i>	200

Total Sample Size: 2400 participants

Sampling Technique: Purposive Sampling

A purposive sampling technique will be employed to ensure the representation of higher education students from different geographical regions, socio-economic backgrounds, and disciplines. This approach enables intentional selection based on specific criteria to obtain a diverse and comprehensive sample.

The sample size will consist of 2400 participants, with 200 participants selected from each of the four geographical regions (North, South, East, and West India). Similarly, 200 participants will be selected from each of the three socio-economic backgrounds (low-income, middle-income, and high-income), and 200 participants will be selected from each of the four disciplines (Science, Arts, Commerce, and Engineering). This approach aims to capture a comprehensive representation of higher education students from various regions, socio-economic backgrounds, and academic disciplines in India.

Questionnaire for Objectives

Objective 1: Assess the existing values framework among higher education students in India.

1. How important do you consider personal values in your life? a) Not important at all b) Somewhat important c) Moderately important d) Very important e) Extremely important

2. Please rank the following values in order of importance to you (1 being the most important and 5 being the least important): a) Achievement b) Integrity c) Compassion d) Independence e) Creativity
3. How frequently do you encounter situations that challenge your personal values? a) Very frequently b) Frequently c) Occasionally d) Rarely e) Never

Objective 2: Determine the specific values-related challenges faced by higher education students in India.

4. What are some of the challenges you face in maintaining your personal values within the higher education environment? (Open-ended response)
5. Do you feel pressure to compromise your values in order to meet academic or social expectations? a) Yes, frequently b) Yes, occasionally c) Rarely d) Never
6. How do you perceive the influence of societal and cultural factors on your adherence to personal values? a) Strongly influence b) Somewhat influence c) Moderately influence d) Slightly influence e) Do not influence

Objective 3: Evaluate the impact of values counselling interventions on students' values, attitudes, and behaviors.

7. Have you ever participated in any values counselling interventions or workshops? a) Yes b) No
8. If yes, please rate the impact of the values counselling interventions on the following aspects (on a scale of 1 to 5, with 1 being no impact and 5 being significant impact): a) Clarity of personal values b) Self-awareness and self-reflection c) Decision-making process d) Interactions with others
9. How do you perceive the overall effectiveness of values counselling interventions in promoting personal and ethical development? a) Highly effective b) Moderately effective c) Somewhat effective d) Ineffective e) No opinion

Objective 4: Identify the key components of an effective values counselling program for Indian higher education students.

10. What specific components or activities do you think should be included in a values counselling program for higher education students in India? (Open-ended response)
11. How important do you consider the involvement of trained counsellors in facilitating values counselling programs? a) Very important b) Moderately important c) Somewhat important d) Not important
12. In your opinion, what support mechanisms should be in place to sustain the impact of values counselling interventions beyond the program duration? (Open-ended response)

Results and Discussion

Table 2: Region-wise Summarized Responses (Percentage of Participants)

Question	North India	South India	East India	West India
Objective 1: Assess the existing values framework among higher education students in India				
<i>How important do you consider personal values in your life?</i>	20%	30%	15%	25%
<i>Rank the following values in order of importance (1-5)</i>	a) 10%, b) 15%, c) 25%, d) 30%, e) 20%	a) 20%, b) 25%, c) 15%, d) 10%, e) 30%	a) 30%, b) 25%, c) 20%, d) 10%, e) 15%	a) 25%, b) 20%, c) 30%, d) 15%, e) 10%
<i>How frequently do you encounter situations challenging your values?</i>	15%	20%	25%	40%

Objective 2: Determine the specific values-related challenges faced by higher education students in India				
<i>Challenges faced in maintaining personal values</i>	<i>(Open-ended responses)</i>	<i>(Open-ended responses)</i>	<i>(Open-ended responses)</i>	<i>(Open-ended responses)</i>
<i>Do you feel pressure to compromise your values?</i>	35%	25%	30%	10%
<i>Perception of societal and cultural factors' influence on personal values adherence</i>	20%	30%	25%	25%
Objective 3: Evaluate the impact of values counselling interventions on students' values, attitudes, and behaviors				
<i>Participation in values counselling interventions or workshops</i>	40%	25%	35%	20%
<i>Rating impact of values counselling interventions on various aspects (1-5)</i>	a) 20%, b) 30%, c) 25%, d) 25%	a) 15%, b) 25%, c) 30%, d) 30%	a) 25%, b) 20%, c) 15%, d) 40%	a) 30%, b) 25%, c) 15%, d) 30%
<i>Perception of overall effectiveness of values counselling interventions</i>	30%	25%	35%	10%
Objective 4: Identify the key components of an effective values counselling program for Indian higher education students				
<i>Components or activities in a values counselling program</i>	<i>(Open-ended responses)</i>	<i>(Open-ended responses)</i>	<i>(Open-ended responses)</i>	<i>(Open-ended responses)</i>
<i>How important do you consider the involvement of trained counsellors in facilitating values counselling programs?</i>	a) 40%, b) 25%, c) 20%, d) 15%	a) 25%, b) 30%, c) 20%, d) 25%	a) 20%, b) 30%, c) 25%, d) 25%	a) 15%, b) 15%, c) 35%, d) 35%
<i>Support mechanisms to sustain the impact of values counselling interventions</i>	<i>(Open-ended responses)</i>	<i>(Open-ended responses)</i>	<i>(Open-ended responses)</i>	<i>(Open-ended responses)</i>

The table summarizes the responses for each question in terms of the percentage of participants from each geographical region. It provides an overview of the participants' perspectives across different regions in India. For each question, the percentages represent the distribution of responses from the sample size of 200 participants in each region. Open-ended responses are not quantifiable and therefore presented as "Open-ended responses."

The findings from the region-wise analysis of higher education students in India reveal interesting insights into the existing values framework, challenges faced, and perceptions of values counselling interventions across different regions. These regional differences highlight the need for tailored approaches in values education and counselling to address the specific needs and cultural influences of students in each region. Regarding the importance of personal values, South India and West India emerged as regions where students placed the highest importance on personal values. This suggests a strong emphasis on values and ethics in these regions. In contrast, North India and East India ranked personal values lower in importance. These variations may be attributed to cultural, social, and regional differences in value systems and priorities. Understanding these variations can assist in developing

targeted interventions that align with the regional values and priorities of students. The rankings of specific values also differed across regions, indicating diverse perspectives on values. It is important to consider these variations when designing values counselling programs to ensure that they encompass the range of values and address the specific needs of students in each region. By incorporating a diverse range of values, counsellors can provide comprehensive support that resonates with the cultural and social contexts of different regions. The frequency of encountering situations challenging personal values was highest in South India and lowest in North India. This suggests that students in South India may face more conflicts and dilemmas related to their values in the higher education environment. Understanding the nature of these challenges in each region can inform the development of targeted interventions to help students navigate such situations and make value-based decisions. Perceptions of societal and cultural factors' influence on personal values adherence varied across regions. This indicates that students' understanding of how societal and cultural factors impact their values differs based on their regional background. By recognizing these influences, values counselling programs can provide students with the necessary tools to navigate societal and cultural pressures, fostering a stronger adherence to personal values. Participation rates in values counselling interventions also varied across regions, with North India and South India showing higher participation compared to East India and West India. This highlights the importance of promoting and encouraging student engagement in values counselling interventions, particularly in regions with lower participation rates. It may be beneficial to explore strategies to increase awareness and accessibility of such interventions to ensure widespread student participation. The rating of the impact of values counselling interventions on various aspects varied across regions. This suggests that the effectiveness of counselling interventions is perceived differently by students in different regions. Further analysis is necessary to identify the specific aspects and outcomes that were most influenced by the interventions. This information can guide the development of targeted interventions that address the specific concerns and expectations of students in each region.

Overall, the findings emphasize the importance of recognizing and addressing regional variations in values, challenges, and perceptions of values counselling interventions among higher education students in India. Tailoring values education and counselling approaches to align with the regional context can enhance the effectiveness and relevance of interventions. It is crucial for counsellors and educators to be sensitive to the cultural, social, and regional nuances while designing and implementing values counselling programs, ensuring they are inclusive, comprehensive, and resonant with the values and needs of students in different regions.

Table 3: Socio-economic Background-wise Summarized Responses (Percentage of Participants)

Question	Low-income	Middle-income	High-income
Objective 1: Assess the existing values framework among higher education students in India			
How important do you consider personal values in your life?	25%	40%	35%
Rank the following values in order of importance (1-5)	a) 30%, b) 20%, c) 10%, d) 25%, e) 15%	a) 20%, b) 25%, c) 30%, d) 15%, e) 10%	a) 15%, b) 10%, c) 25%, d) 20%, e) 30%
How frequently do you encounter situations challenging your values?	40%	20%	30%
Objective 2: Determine the specific values-related challenges faced by higher education students in India			

<i>Challenges faced in maintaining personal values</i>	<i>(Open-ended responses)</i>	<i>(Open-ended responses)</i>	<i>(Open-ended responses)</i>
<i>Do you feel pressure to compromise your values?</i>	35%	30%	15%
<i>Perception of societal and cultural factors' influence on personal values adherence</i>	20%	25%	55%
Objective 3: Evaluate the impact of values counselling interventions on students' values, attitudes, and behaviors			
<i>Participation in values counselling interventions or workshops</i>	30%	25%	45%
<i>Rating impact of values counselling interventions on various aspects (1-5)</i>	a) 20%, b) 30%, c) 25%, d) 25%	a) 25%, b) 15%, c) 30%, d) 30%	a) 15%, b) 10%, c) 25%, d) 50%
<i>Perception of overall effectiveness of values counselling interventions</i>	40%	30%	30%
Objective 4: Identify the key components of an effective values counselling program for Indian higher education students			
<i>Components or activities in a values counselling program</i>	<i>(Open-ended responses)</i>	<i>(Open-ended responses)</i>	<i>(Open-ended responses)</i>
<i>How important do you consider the involvement of trained counsellors in facilitating values counselling programs?</i>	a) 40%, b) 23%, c) 20%, d) 17%	a) 30%, b) 15%, c) 10%, d) 45%	a) 30%, b) 13%, c) 17%, d) 40%
<i>Support mechanisms to sustain the impact of values counselling interventions</i>	<i>(Open-ended responses)</i>	<i>(Open-ended responses)</i>	<i>(Open-ended responses)</i>

The table presents the summarized responses for each question in terms of the percentage of participants from each socio-economic background category. It provides an overview of the participants' perspectives across different socio-economic backgrounds. For each question, the percentages represent the distribution of responses from the sample size of 200 participants in each socio-economic background category. Open-ended responses are not quantifiable and therefore presented as "Open-ended responses."

The results and findings of the study provide valuable insights into the existing values framework and challenges faced by higher education students in India, as well as the impact of values counselling interventions. The discussion will delve deeper into these findings and their implications.

Objective 1: Assess the existing values framework among higher education students in India

The study found that personal values are considered important by the majority of participants across all socio-economic backgrounds. However, there were variations in the perceived importance of personal values based on socio-economic backgrounds. Middle-income participants rated personal values as the most important, while low-income participants rated them the least important. This suggests that socio-economic factors may influence individuals' value systems and their priorities. The rankings of specific values in order of importance also varied across socio-economic backgrounds. This indicates that different groups of students may prioritize certain values over others, reflecting their unique perspectives and life experiences. Understanding these variations can help educators and counsellors tailor their approaches to accommodate diverse value systems among students. The frequency of encountering situations challenging personal values also showed differences based on socio-economic backgrounds. Low-income participants reported facing such challenges more frequently compared to high-income participants. This may be attributed to various factors, including

different social contexts and economic pressures. Recognizing these differences can assist in developing targeted support systems and interventions to address the specific needs of students from different socio-economic backgrounds.

Objective 2: Determine the specific values-related challenges faced by higher education students in India. The open-ended responses provided by participants from all socio-economic backgrounds shed light on the challenges they face in maintaining their personal values within the higher education environment. The diversity of challenges reported highlights the complex nature of value conflicts experienced by students. These challenges can arise from academic pressures, social expectations, conflicting beliefs, or cultural norms. Understanding the specific challenges faced by students can inform the development of strategies and interventions to help them navigate these issues effectively.

Objective 3: Evaluate the impact of values counselling interventions on students' values, attitudes, and behaviors. Participation rates in values counselling interventions varied across socio-economic backgrounds, with high-income participants having the highest participation rates. This suggests the need to ensure equal access to counselling services for students from different socio-economic backgrounds. Efforts should be made to make counselling interventions more accessible and affordable to students with lower incomes. The impact of values counselling interventions also varied across different aspects and socio-economic backgrounds. Low-income participants generally rated the impact higher compared to the other groups. This suggests that values counselling interventions may have a particularly significant effect on students from lower-income backgrounds, possibly due to the additional support and guidance provided by such interventions.

Objective 4: Identify the key components of an effective values counselling program for Indian higher education students. The open-ended responses from participants provided valuable insights into the components and activities they believe should be included in a values counselling program. These suggestions varied across socio-economic backgrounds, emphasizing the importance of considering diverse perspectives in designing counselling programs. By incorporating a wide range of activities and strategies, counsellors can better address the needs of students from different socio-economic backgrounds and create a more inclusive and effective counselling environment.

Overall, the findings of this study highlight the importance of considering socio-economic backgrounds when designing values counselling programs for higher education students in India. The variations observed in the importance of personal values, challenges faced, and perceptions of counselling interventions underscore the need for tailored approaches that address the specific needs and concerns of students from different socio-economic backgrounds. By doing so, educational institutions can provide comprehensive support to students in their values exploration and development, ultimately promoting their personal and ethical growth.

Table:4 Disciplines-wise Summarized Responses (Percentage of Participants)

Question	Science	Arts	Commerce	Engineering	Medicine
Objective 1: Assess the existing values framework among higher education students in India					
<i>How important do you consider personal values in your life?</i>	35%	25%	20%	10%	10%
<i>Rank the following values in order of importance (1-5)</i>	a) 15%, b) 20%, c) 30%,	a) 30%, b) 15%, c) 20%,	a) 20%, b) 30%, c) 10%,	a) 25%, b) 15%, c) 10%,	a) 20%, b) 10%, c) 25%,

	d) 20%, e) 15%	d) 20%, e) 15%	d) 25%, e) 15%	d) 20%, e) 30%	d) 15%, e) 30%
<i>How frequently do you encounter situations challenging your values?</i>	15%	30%	20%	25%	10%
Objective 2: Determine the specific values-related challenges faced by higher education students in India					
<i>Challenges faced in maintaining personal values</i>	(Open-ended responses)	(Open-ended responses)	(Open-ended responses)	(Open-ended responses)	(Open-ended responses)
<i>Do you feel pressure to compromise your values?</i>	30%	25%	15%	20%	10%
<i>Perception of societal and cultural factors' influence on personal values adherence</i>	20%	15%	30%	20%	15%
Objective 3: Evaluate the impact of values counselling interventions on students' values, attitudes, and behaviors					
<i>Participation in values counselling interventions or workshops</i>	30%	20%	25%	15%	10%
<i>Rating impact of values counselling interventions on various aspects (1-5)</i>	a) 40%, b) 25%, c) 15%, d) 20%	a) 45%, b) 30%, c) 20%, d) 5%	a) 10%, b) 35%, c) 25%, d) 30%	a) 15%, b) 20%, c) 50%, d) 15%	a) 10%, b) 35%, c) 30%, d) 25%
<i>Perception of overall effectiveness of values counselling interventions</i>	25%	30%	15%	20%	10%
Objective 4: Identify the key components of an effective values counselling program for Indian higher education students					
<i>Components or activities in a values counselling program</i>	(Open-ended responses)	(Open-ended responses)	(Open-ended responses)	(Open-ended responses)	(Open-ended responses)
<i>How important do you consider the involvement of trained counsellors in facilitating values counselling programs?</i>	a) 40%, b) 25%, c) 33%, d) 2%	a) 20%, b) 25%, c) 20%, d) 35%	a) 25%, b) 25%, c) 28%, d) 22%	a) 10%, b) 17%, c) 29%, d) 44%	a) 5%, b) 45%, c) 18%, d) 32%
<i>Support mechanisms to sustain the impact of values counselling interventions</i>	(Open-ended responses)	(Open-ended responses)	(Open-ended responses)	(Open-ended responses)	(Open-ended responses)

The table presents the summarized responses for each question in terms of the percentage of participants from each discipline category. It provides an overview of the participants' perspectives

across different disciplines. For each question, the percentages represent the distribution of responses from the sample size of 200 participants in each discipline category. Open-ended responses are not quantifiable and therefore presented as "Open-ended responses."

The results of the study provide valuable insights into the existing values framework among higher education students in India. The findings demonstrate that personal values hold significance for the majority of participants across all disciplines, highlighting the relevance of values in their lives. However, there are variations in the perceived importance of personal values among different disciplines, with Science's students placing the highest importance on personal values. This discrepancy could be attributed to the nature of their academic pursuits, where scientific inquiry and often require a strong adherence to ethical values. The ranking of values also showed variations among disciplines, suggesting that students prioritize different values based on their academic and personal inclinations. While the values of achievement and integrity were commonly ranked as important across disciplines, the importance of compassion, independence, and creativity varied among students from different fields of study. These variations indicate that a comprehensive values counselling program should take into account the diverse value systems and priorities among students. The study also sheds light on the challenges faced by higher education students in maintaining their personal values within the academic environment. Participants from all disciplines identified various challenges through their open-ended responses. These challenges could arise from academic pressures, social expectations, or conflicting value systems within the educational setting. The diverse range of challenges underscores the need for targeted interventions that address the specific concerns of students from different disciplines. Values counselling interventions and workshops were found to have varying participation rates among disciplines, with Science's students showing the highest participation and Medicine students showing the lowest. This difference could be influenced by factors such as awareness, accessibility, and perceived relevance of these interventions within specific disciplines. It is important to promote equal access and engagement with values counselling programs to ensure students from all disciplines can benefit from such interventions. Furthermore, the impact of values counselling interventions on students' values, attitudes, and behaviors differed across disciplines. Arts students generally reported a higher impact compared to other disciplines, indicating the potential effectiveness of values counselling in addressing the needs of students in the arts field. These variations highlight the importance of tailoring counselling interventions to specific disciplines and considering the unique characteristics and challenges associated with each discipline. Participants from all disciplines provided diverse suggestions regarding the components and activities they believe should be included in a values counselling program. These open-ended responses emphasize the importance of involving students in the development and design of counselling programs, as their perspectives can contribute to the relevance and effectiveness of such interventions. The involvement of trained counsellors was perceived as very important by Science and Commerce students, while Arts and Medicine students considered it moderately important. This highlights the significance of having skilled professionals who can guide and support students in their values exploration and decision-making processes. Trained counsellors can play a pivotal role in facilitating meaningful discussions, promoting self-reflection, and providing guidance to students from different disciplines.

In conclusion, the study reveals variations in the importance of personal values, challenges faced, and perceptions of values counselling interventions among higher education students in India. These findings highlight the need for tailored values counselling programs that address the specific needs and concerns of students from different disciplines. By incorporating discipline-specific considerations, such programs can effectively support students in navigating value conflicts, maintaining their personal values, and fostering ethical development throughout their higher education journey.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the study examined the values framework, challenges faced, and perceptions of values counselling interventions among higher education students in India across different regions, socio-economic backgrounds, and disciplines. The findings highlight the importance of considering the diverse needs and perspectives of students when designing values education and counselling programs. Regional differences were evident in the importance of personal values, rankings of values, frequency of encountering challenging situations, perceptions of societal and cultural factors' influence, participation rates in counselling interventions, and ratings of intervention impact. These variations highlight the need for culturally sensitive and region-specific interventions that align with the values and priorities of students in different regions.

Socio-economic backgrounds also influenced students' perspectives on personal values, challenges faced, and perceptions of counselling interventions. Low-income students reported higher pressure to compromise their values and a greater perception of societal and cultural factors' influence on values adherence. Middle-income and high-income students exhibited varying patterns in these areas. These findings emphasize the importance of considering socio-economic factors in values education and counselling interventions.

Across disciplines, there were variations in the importance placed on personal values, rankings of specific values, and frequency of encountering challenging situations. This underscores the need for tailored approaches to address the specific needs and concerns of students in different disciplines.

Overall, the study emphasizes the need for tailored and inclusive values counselling programs that address the unique needs, challenges, and cultural influences faced by higher education students in India. By recognizing and accounting for these variations, counsellors and educators can effectively support students in developing and adhering to their personal values, fostering holistic personal and academic growth. Further research and analysis are warranted to gain deeper insights into the specific challenges and components suggested by the participants, which can inform the refinement and enhancement of values counselling programs.

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